

Three Additional 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Fragments

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James R. Davila (1994) published as the manuscript 4Q1 or 4QGen-Exod^a an assemblage of fragments, preserving parts of Genesis 22 through Exodus 8 and written in the same hand, which earlier editors had brought together. As holds true for many Qumran Cave 4 manuscripts, additional fragments should be added to the edition. This short note presents three small fragments, placed on the museum plates of unidentified fragments, which should be added to 4Q1 and can be joined to already published 4Q1 fragments

1 PAM 43.678 frag. 51. Join to 4Q1 frag. 22 i. Exod 4:6-7

The editors of the volume with Qumran Cave 4 unidentified fragments already identified PAM 43.678 frag. 51 (Pike and Skinner 2001, 130-31), but most subsequent scholarship has overlooked their identification. Textually and materially the fragments join perfectly.

4Q1 frag. 22 i (section) left; PAM 43.678 frag. 51 right
images taken from the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-362061>
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492715>

One should now transcribe the left end of 4Q1 frags. 21-22 i + PAM 43.678 frag. 51 lines 4-5 as follows:

מחיקו והנ[ה ידו] מצרעת	4
א[ל ח[יקו ו]י[צאהו] מחיקו	5

2 PAM 43.697 frag. 84. Join to 4Q1 frag. 25 i. Exod 4:27–28

The hitherto unidentified fragment PAM 43.697 frag. 84 joins textually and materially to 4Q1 frag. 25 i lines 3-4.

4Q1 frag. 25 (left) and PAM 43.697 frag. 84 (right)

images taken from the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284246> (PAM 43.006)

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285122> (PAM 43.697)

One should now transcribe the left end of 4Q1 frags. 24-25 i + PAM 43.697 frag. 84 lines 3-4 as follows:

[אהרן לך] לקראת מ[שה המדברה וילך ויפגשו בהר 3
לאה] וְאֵת כָּל דְּבָרֵי יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר שָׁלַח 4

3 PAM 43.692 frag. 14. Join to 4Q1 frag. 35. Exod 7:17-18

The hitherto unidentified fragment PAM 43.692 frag. 14 joins textually and materially to the bottom of 4Q1 frag. 35, and textually to the left of 4Q1 frag. 34.

4Q1 frag. 24 (top) and PAM 43.692 frag. 14 (bottom)
images taken from the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-362193>
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-503147>

One should now transcribe 4Q1 frags. 34-35 and PAM 43.692 frag. 14 line 4 as follows:

[בידי על] המים אשר ביאר ונהפ[כו] לדם וה[דגה] 4

4 Schøyen MS 5439/1. Gen 37:8

The fragment MS 5439/1 from the Schøyen collection was initially assigned to 4Q1 (Puech 2011) but subsequently, and more plausibly, to 4Q364 (Elgvin 2016, 153-58).

Bibliography

- Davila, James A. "1. 4QGen-Exod^a." In Eugene Ulrich et al., eds. *Qumran Cave 4. VII: Genesis to Numbers*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 12 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994), 7-30, pls. I-V.
- Elgvin, Torleif et al., eds. *Gleanings from the Caves: Dead Sea Scrolls and Artefacts from The Schøyen Collection* (London: Bloomsbury, 2016).

Pike, Dana M., and Andrew C. Skinner. *Qumran Cave 4.XXIII: Unidentified Fragments, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001).

Puech, Émile. "Un nouveau fragment 7a de 4QGn-Ex^a = 4QGn-Ex 1 et quelques nouvelles lectures et identifications du manuscrit 4Q1." *Revue de Qumran* 25/97 (2011), 103-12.